

1 **Supplementary Information**

2 ***Coding Dictionary***

3 **S1 – Preprocessing codes**

4 The following codes were applied during initial coding to find the relevant interview text for analysis. We first identified text triple
5 coded to “Decision,” either “Sustainability” or “Fire resilience,” and either “for” or “against.” We then found the corresponding
6 influencing factors (Table S3), double coding them to “Influencing factor” and either “Enabler” or “Barrier.” Note that for
7 frequency analysis, we only counted influencing factors that went the same direction as a decision. For example, if a homeowner
8 purchased a metal fence (decision for fire resilience) despite not wanting to pay the extra financial cost (influencing factor barrier),
9 cost would not be counted as an influencing factor.

10 **Table S1**

Subcode	Parent Code	Definition
Sustainability	Decision	Rebuilding decisions related to sustainability (see Table 1 for full list of decisions). Coded as either for (increasing sustainability) or against (not increasing sustainability).
Fire Resilience	Decision	Rebuilding decisions related to fire resilience (see Table 1 for full list of decisions). Coded as either for (increasing fire resilience) or against (not increasing fire resilience).
Enabler	Influencing factor	Influencing factors that helped or led to the homeowner making a decision for sustainability or fire resilience.
Barrier	Influencing factor	Influencing factors that hindered or prevented the homeowner making a decision for sustainability or fire resilience.

11
12
13
14
15
16
17

18 S2 – Influencing factor parent codes (affinity groups).

19 **Table S2**

Parent Code	Definition
Self-efficacy	Belief in one's ability to carry out a decision.
Response costs	Perceived short-term burdens or benefits that shaped the attractiveness of a decision.
Outcome expectancy	Perceived long-term effectiveness or value of a decision.
Other	Influences outside of coping appraisal theory (e.g., fire experience, connection to climate change).

20

21 S3 – Influencing factor subcodes

22 Frequencies were based on the number of participants who mentioned a given influence subcode, with each participant counted
 23 only once per influence subcode within a decisional class. We distinguished four decisional classes: sustainability–enabler,
 24 sustainability–barrier, fire resilience–enabler, and fire resilience–barrier. Accordingly, the same influence subcode (e.g., “builder
 25 influence”) could appear in more than one decisional class, meaning that a participant could contribute up to four counts for that
 26 subcode if it was mentioned in each class.

27 **Table S3**

Subcode	Parent Code	Definition
Builder influence	Self-efficacy	Homeowner perception of their builder's capacity, builder persuasion, or homeowner trust in their builder.
Financial cost	Self-efficacy/ Response costs	Costs and perceptions of costs that can make decisions more or less feasible (self-efficacy) or attractive (response costs).
Insurance payout	Self-efficacy/ Response costs	Whether insurance will cover the decision, or clarity about coverage.
Incentives/aid	Self-efficacy/ Response costs	Grants, rebates, or aid that influence adoption.
Simplicity (effort)	Self-efficacy/ Response costs	Simplicity or complexity of implementation.

Expediency (time)	Self-efficacy/ Response costs	Time required to implement decision; urgency may inhibit a adoption.
Rebuilding opportunity	Response costs	The idea that the act of rebuilding provided a rare chance to implement sustainability or fire resilience features that might not have been feasible outside a full reconstruction scenario due to cost, timing, or structural limitations.
Primary expectancy	Outcome expectancy	Assessment of whether a sustainability feature (e.g., insulation, solar panels, or heat pump) will provide adequate energy efficiency improvements, electricity generation, or heating/cooling, depending on the decision under consideration.
Safety expectancy	Outcome expectancy	Assessment of whether a fire-resilient feature (e.g., materials, sprinklers) will provide wildfire safety.
Environmental benefits	Outcome expectancy	Assessment or belief in the environmental benefits provided by a sustainability feature.
Investment worth	Outcome expectancy	Assessment of whether an investment related to a sustainability or fire-resilience feature will pay off financially.
Other benefits/issues	Outcome expectancy	Assessment of comfort, health, maintenance, functionality, or other long-term expected outcomes of a sustainability or fire resilience feature.
Fire experience	Other	Lived experience surviving the fire, especially relating to changes in perception, risk assessment, or priorities.
Technology experience	Other	Prior experience with technology which affects confidence or perception of technology worth.
Climate change connection	Other	Views on climate change as a motivating factor for sustainability or fire resilience features.
Risk assessment	Other	Assessment of present or future fire risk.

28

29

30

31

32 S4 - Characterization of possible sustainability and fire resilience rebuilding decisions.

33 **Table S4**

Characterization of Rebuilding Decisions	
Sustainability	Fire Resilience
<p>Efficiency</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Envelope improvements (insulation, windows, doors, sealing/air tightness) - High efficiency appliances (like an induction range) - Air tightness/sealing - House size - Material longevity 	<p>Fire Resistant Materials/Design</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Exterior Cladding - Patios/decks (wood vs. no deck or non-flammable options) - Roofing (i.e., metal roof vs. standard class A composite shingle) - Fire resistant windows - Internal structure (treated lumber or other non-flammable options such as concrete) - Limited penetrations - Mesh over vents - Fire-resistant eave designs (closed eaves) or no eaves - Gutter guards or no gutters - Home orientation
<p>Energy Type/Source</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Renewables (solar panels or solar ready, EV charger or EV charger ready, battery bank) - Gas hookup (could be for heating, fireplace, range, and/or grill) - Electric heat pump - Geothermal heat pump 	<p>Fire Resistant Vegetation/Landscaping</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited vegetation close to home - Native and fire-resistant vegetation - Fire safe landscaping like no mulch, zero-scape, or lots of rock - Maintaining 3-5 feet of defensible space - Fencing (wood versus no fence or non-flammable options)
<p>Standards</p>	<p>Fire Sprinklers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fire sprinklers (Mandatory for Unincorporated Boulder County)

- | | |
|--|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Energy code adopted (IECC 2018 vs. IECC 2021, Unincorporated Boulder County not applicable) - Utility rebates sought corresponding to various tiers at or above IECC 2021 | |
|--|--|

34

35 S5 - Homeowner rebuilding decisions follow-up interview script

36 The following interview script was used as a reference guide in semi-structured interviews with study participants.

37

38 Interview Topics/Questions

39

40 *Preamble*

- 41 • Is it okay if I start recording?

42 Consent

- 43 • Before we get started, I want to let you know your participation is anonymous and voluntary. We can stop at any time, and you don't have to answer any questions you don't want to. You can also withdraw your participation until publication. Do you have any questions? May I have your consent to speak with me?

46 Explanation of the current round of follow-ups:

- 47 • The first round of interviews was to gain insight into the rebuilding challenges and plans of homeowners. Now we're looking at what decisions were actually made and what may have changed since we last spoke. We're mainly focused on outcomes relating to sustainability and fire resilience. We know there was controversy surrounding some of these decisions, and we want to understand people's choices.

51 *Main*

52

53 Decisions and changes

- 54 • To get us started, how are things going for you? Have you finished rebuilding?
- 55 • How do you feel about your rebuild?
- 56 • When we first spoke, you mentioned wanting to do ____ and _____. Were you able to do those things?
 - 57 o Previously, you mentioned the reasons for doing these things were _____. Do you still see that as the case?
 - 58 o Are there any other energy efficiency or fire-resistant features you were able to incorporate (i.e. codes, building materials, etc.)?
 - 60 ♣ [See list of possible decisions below if needed]
 - 61 ♣ What influenced your decisions (i.e., costs, incentives, neighbors, builder, etc.)?
- 62 • As you were rebuilding, did you make any significant changes or shift direction? If so, why?
- 63 • Did you need to make tradeoffs with rebuilding decisions (for example, did cost, or cost uncertainty lead you to make different choices in your rebuilding decisions such as energy efficiency? How did you make these decisions?

64

65 Community

- 66 • What things did you work with others on and what did you do by yourself?
 - 67 o [Prompt if needed]: For instance, did you consider hiring the same builder as your neighbors? Why? Why not?
 - 68 o How did you decide on common materials, such as fencing, with your neighbors?
 - 69 • What influenced that?
- 70 • When would you recommend others rebuilding post-fire collaborate, and when would you recommend going it alone?
- 71 Why?
- 72 • What ongoing discussions are happening that you are a part of?

73 Lessons learned

- 74 • Knowing what you know now about the rebuilding process, would you have made any different choices?
- 75 • Is there anything you wish your community had done differently?

76 Builder

- 77 • Last we spoke, you had decided to go with _____ builder. How did that go?
 - 78 o How did your builder impact your rebuilding decisions related to sustainability and fire resilience, if at all?

79 **End**

- 80 • Would it be okay if I contacted you again if I have any more questions?

81

82 **List of potential sustainability and fire resilience decisions**

83

84 Sustainability:

85

86 Adopted energy code

- 87 • 2018 IECC (Louisville and Superior)
- 88 • 2021 IECC (Louisville and Superior)
- 89 • 2021 IECC + Net Zero (Louisville and Superior)
- 90 • Boulder County BuildSmart (Unincorporated Boulder County)
- 91 • Boulder County BuildSmart Zero Net Energy (Unincorporated Boulder County)

92 Other

- 93 • Solar panels
- 94 • Solar ready
- 95 • EV charger
- 96 • EV ready
- 97 • All electric
- 98 • Electric heat pumps for home heating and cooling
- 99 • Windows with R-value greater than required by code (more energy efficient)
- 100 • Extra/above required insulation
- 101 • Net zero energy
- 102 • Passive solar design

103 Fire resilience:

104
105 Potential alignment with wildland-urban interface codes

- 106 • Indoor sprinklers
- 107 • General ignition-resistant or non-flammable building materials
- 108 • Class A roof
- 109 • Fire resistant Eaves, and Gutters and Downspouts
- 110 • Fire-resistant deck
- 111 • Fire rated windows
- 112 • Ember resistant vents
- 113 • Non-combustible fencing
- 114 • Defensible space (no combustible materials within 5 ft)

115 Other

- 116 • Fire-resistant or ember-resistant siding, e.g. fiber cement siding
- 117 • Fire-resistant windows: Triple-pane or dual-pane windows with metal-clad or fiberglass frames
- 118 • In-home sprinkler systems
- 119 • Non-combustible or fire-resistant decking, e.g., PVC, composite, concrete, fire retardant treated wood, etc.
- 120 • Defensible space: Non-combustible fencing materials (e.g., metal, fire retardant treated materials, etc.) or landscaping
- 121 (e.g., fences, vegetation, fire breaks, etc.) within 5 feet of a residential structure
- 122 • Gutter guards
- 123 • Ember-resistant vents
- 124 • Mitigation measures for other hazards (flood, wind, etc.)